

Relative abundance of five rice stem borer species on each crop of a triple-rice pattern in Iloilo, Philippines

M.D. Lumaban, research assistant, and J.A. Litsinger, associate entomologist, Entomology Department, Cropping Systems Program, International Rice Research Institute

With supplemental irrigation, three rice crops are being grown in low-lying fields of Iloilo, a rainfed lowland rice area. Stem borer populations for the crop year 1975-76 were monitored on each crop (IR28) by dissecting deadhearts and whiteheads. Five species were recorded; the predominant species was the white stem borer (WSB) *Scirpophaga innotata* (see figure). The yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas*, second in abundance, was predominant in the first and third crops. The striped stem borer (SSB) *Chilo suppressalis* was the third most abundant, its numbers declined, however, during the third rice crop. The pink stem borer (PSB) *Sesamia inferens* was fourth most abundant and the gold fringed borer (GFB) *Chilo auricilius* (not the dark headed stem borer *C. polychrysus*) was fifth. As current IR varieties are only moderately resistant, stem borer control will have to be based on insecticides.

